

Conference Abstract

Habitat enhancement for the mud loach (*Misgurnus fossilis*) - project details, construction process and results of fish monitoring

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Abstract

The drainage ditch system in the foreland of the rivers March and Thaya in the municipalities of Rabensburg and Hohenau an der March represents together with a number of relict watercourses an important wetland area on the edge of the floodplain.

Based on observations made in the course of repeated ditch clearings in Hohenau and recent targeted searches, it is known that this water system represents an important habitat for the protected and endangered mud loach (*Misgurnus fossilis*). In recent years, long periods of drought have led to the drying up of a large part of the existing water network, until finally only the so-called main ditch still carries water, leaving a very small remnant of the overall system for the mud loach as a refuge. Various measures were developed and implemented on behalf of the AURING association to counteract this increasingly precarious disappearance of the aquatic habitat in the ditches. For example, dam beams were installed at critical points in the ditch system to dam up the water in the ditch system and thus improve the habitat for the mud loach and maintain the ditches as habitats even during dry periods. Connections between ditches, which were originally open but have since silted up, and adjacent suttens as spawning and juvenile fish habitats were also restored by dredging (Suppl. material 1). The entire construction process was supervised by biologists. In order to document the impact of the measures, a

comprehensive performance review was carried out, including fish monitoring, monitoring of water temperature, habitat mapping and assessment, and monitoring of effects of measures on amphibians and dragonflies.

The population of the mud loach was surveyed before and after the construction measures were implemented, using electrofishing. The results show that mud loach was detected in some of the optimised habitats just a few months after construction work was completed. In addition to electrofishing, the migration of fish into and out of the ditch system was also investigated using fish traps. In combination with the results of water temperature monitoring, there appears to be a strong correlation between fish populations in the project area and the groundwater level.

Keywords

mud loach, weatherfish, habitat enhancement, groundwater influence, spawning habitats, ditch system, dam beams, ditch clearings, water temperature monitoring, electrofishing, Hohenau an der March, fish traps, March, Thaya

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Habitat enhancement for the mud loach (*Misgurnus fossilis*) - project details, construction process and results of fish monitoring [doi](#)

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